

InterKult 2020

THE 6th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

INTERCULTURALISM IN EDUCATION

Book of Abstracts

PEDAGOGICAL INSTITUTE OF VOJVODINA

Novi Sad, October 3rd, 2020

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Pedagoški
zavod
Vojvodine

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Editor: Msc. Silvia Ilić

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Interkulturalno obrazovanje - unapređenje profesionalne prakse u sistemu obrazovanja učitelja u multikulturalnom društvu

Jedan od najznačajnijih faktora održivog razvoja društva je vaspitanje i obrazovanje mladih generacija. U multikulturalnom društvu kao što je Vojvodina, poseban značaj pridaje se negovanju s jedne strane nacionalnog identiteta, a s druge društvenoj koheziji u smislu negovanja duha zajedništva među pripadnicima različitih kultura u vidu interkulturalnog obrazovanja. Isto tako značajan faktor efikasnosti vaspitno-obrazovnih institucija čine kompetencije nastavnog osoblja. U tom smislu u studijskim programima za obrazovanje vaspitača i učitelja veoma značajnu ulogu ima kvalitetna praktična nastava. Cilj ovog istraživanja je ispitivanje kvaliteta praktične nastave Učiteljskog fakulteta na mađarskom nastavnom jeziku u Subotici u svetlu novih zahteva Nacionalnog akreditacionog tela u pravcu izrade novih strategija obrazovanja, kojima bi se ne samo značajno povećao broj časova praktične nastave već se i preosmislila saradnja i povezanost Fakulteta i predškolskih ustanova kao i škola vežbaonica, i to na teritoriji cele Vojvodine gde se izvodi nastava na mađarskom nastavnom jeziku. Nadalje, naglasak se posebno stavlja na razvoj onih specifičnih kompetencija vaspitača i učitelja koje će im omogućiti uspešno funkcionisanje u multikulturalnim sredinama gde bi uz očuvanje i negovanje specifičnosti vlastitog nacionalnog identiteta nastojali razvijati naročito interkulturalne kompetencije, kao nezamenljive spone integrativnih funkcija za multikulturalne

društvene sredine kakva je Vojvodina.

Ključne reči: praktična nastava, multikulturalna sredina, interkulturalne kompetencije, integrativne funkcije

Intercultural education – the development of professional teaching practice in the education system of pre-service teachers in a multicultural environment

Education of young generations is one of the most important factors of sustainable development in a society. In a multicultural society – as for instance Vojvodina – it is of high importance to nurture national identity as well as fellowship among various cultures for the purpose of social cohesion. In addition, educational institutions establish the intercultural competences of teachers, therefore teaching practice has a crucial role in curriculum of teachers and pre-school teachers. The purpose of the present research is to elicit the quality of practice teaching of the Hungarian Language Teacher Training Faculty in Subotica from the perspective of the new request stated by the National Entity for Accreditation that entitles the development of new strategic education program which increases the number of practice teaching classes among pre-service teachers and kindergarten teachers as well as reconsiders the co-operation between the Faculty and pre-school/primary school institutions on the territory of Vojvodina where education is realized in Hungarian. Furthermore, it is important to highlight the specific competences of pre-school and primary school teachers that will enable them to successfully perform in a multicultural environment in which along the preservation and nurture of individual national identities intercultural competences could also emerge as essential basis for an integrative functioning of a multicultural society, such as Vojvodina.

Keywords: teaching practice, multicultural environment, intercultural competence, integrative functions

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